

Resource Allocation as a Market: A Case Study on Multi-Server Multi-Model Federated Learning

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Abstract—6G networks envision a seamless integration of data and AI into their core operations, marking a new era where distributed client devices actively engage in intelligent processes, supported by a diverse ecosystem of AI service providers. This shift necessitates approaching traditional resource allocation problems from a market perspective, transparently reflecting the gains and losses of clients and providers within the ecosystem. In this paper, we use a multi-server, multi-model Federated Learning (FL) network as a case study to propose a market-based resource allocation framework. The framework models the joint problem of client resource allocation and pricing as a Fisher market, where servers compete to attract clients with private data and local computing resources for distributed model training. The joint problem is formulated as a convex program, aiming to maximize the total server utility related to their model’s accuracy, while incorporating clients’ total computing resource constraints and servers’ budget constraints. An analytical solution to the convex program is derived concluding the so-called Market Equilibrium (ME) point, where market clearance is achieved. The effectiveness of the proposed market-based resource allocation framework is validated through comparisons with established resource allocation and sharing schemes from the literature.

Index Terms—Multi-server multi-model federated learning, pricing, resource allocation, Fisher market, Market Equilibrium.

I. INTRODUCTION

6G distinguishes itself from previous generations through its inherent data-driven architecture, where vast amounts of data are generated, processed, and utilized to enable Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered services across various applications. These range from user-centric services to network optimization tasks, such as resource allocation and predictive maintenance. On the one hand, the growing demand to harness the data for advanced AI-driven solutions leads to the emergence of numerous AI service providers [1]. On the other hand, the data are inherently private and belong to individual clients, highlighting the urgent need for privacy-preserving mechanisms to ensure data security, such as Federated Learning (FL) [2]. This creates a novel market landscape where client participation becomes a cornerstone for enabling local model training. Nevertheless, the coexistence of multiple service providers and diverse AI

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models introduces significant challenges in resource allocation, necessitating intelligent strategies to manage clients’ computational resources efficiently.

In this paper, we investigate the resource allocation problem within the emerging 6G landscape, focusing on its market dimension. Toward this direction, we consider a multi-server, multi-model FL network as a proof of concept for efficiently allocating the computing resources of clients to multiple concurrently trained models. The clients are assumed to have local datasets for training these models but differ in their heterogeneous computing capabilities, which directly influence the payments they receive as incentives for participating in the FL process. The servers train models of varying criticality and operate under budget constraints. In this context, we provide a tangible answer to the intricate problem of *how to efficiently determine the clients’ prices and allocate their limited computing resources to the competing servers, ensuring both model priority and fairness*.

A. Related Work and Motivation

The incentive-based interaction between clients and central servers is well-explored in the FL market literature. Extensive work can be found, scrutinizing various incentive forms, such as resource or monetary rewards, while targeting objectives like computational energy, latency, and learning accuracy [3]. Additionally, considerable efforts have focused on the mechanisms used for providing these incentives, heavily resorting to economic and game-theoretic models that effectively capture market interactions [4]. For instance, the works in [5], [6] proposed auction frameworks to select clients and their payments toward maximizing social welfare measured by factors like data quality, communication costs, and payments. The hierarchical nature of the market can be further modeled as a Stackelberg game as in [7], where the distribution of IoT sensors’ sensing data to different edge servers is optimized along with their pricing to maximize revenue and minimize energy consumption. Contract theory is another commonly used theoretical framework for incentive provisioning between a principal – as it is termed – and multiple agents, which has been also applied in [8] for FL in the internet-of-vehicles.

Remarkably, though, only a few research works have delved into the market dynamics of multi-server multi-model FL networks, where the competition among multiple servers introduces an additional degree of freedom that significantly impacts the outcomes of resource allocation. However, to be more precise, even these works completely neglect modeling multi-server competition and place their focus primarily on the distribution of clients to servers. Indicatively, in [9], the joint problem of FL participant selection and learning topology determination is addressed, enabling multiple models to select their participants across real-world networks to minimize learning costs. In [10], client scheduling for multi-model training over time and network resource allocation are jointly tackled in real-world settings where clients continuously collect and discard data while having distinct communication/computing characteristics. Beyond resource allocation and client selection or scheduling, other research focuses on protocol design and extensions for multi-model FL scenarios. A key area of interest is Over-the-Air Computation (OTA), a primary technique for transmitting local model parameters in wireless FL networks [11].

However, the coexistence of multiple servers belonging to different providers and training different models creates inherent competition in attracting clients that maximize individual model accuracy under budget constraints, where the budget may represent resources or monetary rewards. This resource allocation problem can be modeled as a Fisher market [12], where a set of buyers, i.e., servers, aim to purchase multiple goods in the sense of clients' computing resources to maximize their utility while operating under constrained budget availability. In a Fisher market, the prices and allocation of goods are derived to clear the market, meaning that the goods are optimally allocated to maximize the buyers' utility and fairly priced such that the corresponding sellers would not deviate from the resulting allocation. The latter equilibrium point is referred to as Market Equilibrium (ME). So far, ME-based resource allocation approaches have been proposed for network slicing and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) in [13], [14], where the ME is determined including the prices and the allocation of compute and radio resources to maximize the number and minimize the processing delay of end-user computation requests in a network. Recently, the work in [15] further applied the ME theory to facilitate knowledge sharing between multiple providers of AI services that buy and sell model parameters of trained models.

B. Contributions and Outline

This paper is motivated by the notably limited literature on resource allocation in multi-server multi-model FL networks, overlooking the inherent competition between servers training different models during decision-making. Simultaneously, in this paper, we strive to address the critical issue of incentive provisioning to clients, ensuring the viability of the FL process. To this end, we propose a market-based computing resource allocation and pricing solution, modeling the servers as buyers who invest their budgets to incentivize clients to

Fig. 1: Overview of multi-server multi-model FL market.

participate in FL and allocate fractions of their computing power to train the servers' models. The computing resource allocations and client prices are determined based on the Market Equilibrium (ME), where servers maximize their utility by obtaining fractions of computing resources that enhance the accuracy of their respective models. The clients, in turn, are priced fairly so that no other allocation would be more beneficial for them. Specifically, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- 1) The joint problem of computing resource allocation and incentive provisioning in a multi-server multi-model FL network is modeled as a Fisher market, leveraging the theory of ME, aiming to optimize the accuracy of the different servers' models.
- 2) The joint resource allocation and pricing problem is formulated as a convex program that incorporates clients' total computing resource constraints and servers' budget constraints, ensuring convergence to the ME point.
- 3) An analytical solution to the convex program is derived using duality theory to determine the equilibrium resource allocations and prices.
- 4) Extensive numerical results from modeling and simulation demonstrate the behavior of the proposed market under varying client resources and server budget constraints at the ME while benchmarking its performance against other established resource allocation and sharing schemes from the literature.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the modeling of a multi-server multi-model FL network as a market and formulates the resource allocation and pricing problem. Section III explains the concept of the ME point and presents a convex program, along with its analytical solution, to determine the equilibrium allocations and prices. Section IV presents the performance evaluation of the proposed framework and Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a multi-server multi-model FL network, as shown in Fig. 1, comprising a set of clients $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n, \dots, N\}$ and a set of servers $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, m, \dots, M\}$. Clients can range from Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices, autonomous vehicles, and user-owned devices to enterprises or organizations. The clients are assumed to possess a substantial volume of data collected from diverse perspectives, which can be leveraged to train various models tailored to specific contexts. For instance, from the same pool of data, tasks like object detection (e.g., identifying pedestrians or stop signs) and image classification (e.g., recognizing types of vehicles or road conditions) can be performed, enabling the development of versatile and context-aware AI models. In this context, the servers, each responsible for training different models, seek to actively collaborate with the clients and motivate them to participate in the FL process.

Let F_n [CPU cycles/sec] indicate the computing power of client n , which is the primary parameter differentiating clients from one another. The total computing power of each client n can be divided into multiple resource slots, each allocated a specific fraction of the total computing power F_n . These slots allow the client to concurrently train multiple models, with each allocated a dedicated share of the total power F_n , denoted as $\alpha_{n,m}F_n$, where $\alpha_{n,m} \in [0, 1]$ is the fraction of computing power allocated to the model of server m , such that $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \alpha_{n,m}F_n \leq F_n, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.

Assuming that client n possesses $D_{n,m}$ training samples for server's m model, with a computational intensity of $C_{n,m}$ [CPU cycles/sample], the total computing time for training the model of server m locally on client n is expressed as:

$$T_{n,m}^{loc} = \frac{\log\left(\frac{1}{\delta_{n,m}}\right) D_{n,m} C_{n,m}}{\alpha_{n,m} F_n} \text{ [sec]}, \quad (1)$$

where $\log\left(\frac{1}{\delta_{n,m}}\right)$ is the expected number of local model update iterations required to achieve an error rate of $\delta_{n,m}$ [16], with small values of $\delta_{n,m}$ implying high accuracy $q_{n,m} = \frac{1}{\delta_{n,m}}$ for the model and vice versa.

The FL process requires multiple iterations for the global model to achieve an acceptable level of accuracy. During each FL iteration, local model training is conducted on the client side. The model parameters or gradients from each client are then sent to the server for global model aggregation. Following this, the local models are updated, and the next FL iteration begins. However, the specific details of the FL iterations and the associated communications are not the focus of this work. The overall multi-model FL process can utilize established state-of-the-art approaches, e.g., [9]–[11].

A. Market and Utility Model

The computing resource allocation problem is modeled as a Fisher market [12], where the servers act as buyers and the clients' computing resources represent the goods purchased. The purchases of each server are indicated by the vector $\alpha_m = [a_{1,m}, \dots, a_{n,m}, \dots, a_{N,m}]$ in the sense that a client n allocates a fraction $\alpha_{n,m}$ from its computing resources to

facilitate the distributed model training of server's m model. Each client n is priced at p_n by the market to compensate for the local model training that it offers while taking into account the budget B_m of each edge server. Apparently, the price vector $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_n, \dots, p_N]$ regulates the market by controlling the competition between the servers and the clients.

The market is characterized by a set of constraints that govern the resource allocation and pricing dynamics. On the one hand, the computing resource allocation from the client side is limited by the total computing power of each client, such that $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \alpha_{n,m} \leq 1, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. On the other hand, each buyer, i.e., server, is restricted by a fixed budget B_m , with high budget values indicating greater model criticality and priority. This means that servers with more critical tasks or higher-priority applications are willing to pay more and acquire additional computing resources to achieve faster local model training (see Eq. (1)). Therefore, the budget constraint $\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_{n,m} p_n \leq B_m, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$ must be satisfied.

Each server m has a utility function to quantify the benefit obtained from the computing resource allocation of client n for local model training. As rational entities, the servers seek to maximize their utility, representing the improvement in global model accuracy achieved through a specific amount of allocated computing resources. Specifically, in this paper, we consider the linear profit/utility function of a server m :

$$U_m(\mathbf{a}_m) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} q_{n,m} a_{n,m}, \quad (2)$$

where $q_{n,m}$ is the gain that server m achieved from employing client n , while $\alpha_{n,m}$ is the fraction of allocated computing resources from client n to server m . Note that extensions of the market model to incorporate more sophisticated utility functions, which capture the complex relationships arising from resource substitution within a single server, such as the so-called Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) function [12], are part of our current and future work.

Concerning the gain $q_{n,m}$ of server m from client n , this corresponds to the local model accuracy achieved by client n . High values of $q_{n,m}$ have the potential to enhance the overall global model accuracy at server m . Specifically, given a local training time threshold $T_{n,m}^{thr}$ [sec] specified by server m for training its model across all clients, the accuracy $q_{n,m}$ achieved by client n from allocating a fraction $\alpha_{n,m}$ of its computing resources is calculated as:

$$q_{n,m} = \frac{1}{\delta_{n,m}} = 2^{\frac{T_{n,m}^{thr} \alpha_{n,m} F_n}{D_{n,m} C_{n,m}}} \approx \frac{T_{n,m}^{thr} \alpha_{n,m} F_n}{D_{n,m} C_{n,m}}, \quad (3)$$

as a direct consequence of Eq. (1). The last term in Eq. (3) serves as an approximation introduced for numerical convenience, justified by the monotonically increasing trend of the exponential function.

B. Problem Formulation

The utility maximization problem to determine the optimal resource allocation $\alpha_m^* = [a_{1,m}, \dots, a_{n,m}, \dots, a_{N,m}], \forall m \in$

\mathcal{M} in the Fisher market at prices $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_n, \dots, p_N]$ is formally defined as follows:

$$\max_{\alpha_{n,m} \geq 0, \forall n,m} \sum_{\forall m \in \mathcal{M}} U_m \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{\forall m \in \mathcal{M}} a_{n,m} \leq 1, \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (4b)$$

$$\sum_{\forall n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_{n,m} p_n \leq B_m, \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (4c)$$

where the objective is to maximize the total utility of all servers, subject to constraints that ensure the resource allocation is within the servers' budgets (Eq. (4b)) and the clients' available computing resources (Eq. (4c)). Nevertheless, the ultimate goal of this paper is to determine the ME point, which is presented analytically in the following section.

III. RESOURCE ALLOCATION FOR MULTI-SERVER MULTI-MODEL FL BASED ON MARKET EQUILIBRIUM

This section introduces the Market Equilibrium (ME) point, which represents the equilibrium state of the Fisher market model and the resource allocation problem, described earlier in Section II. First, the definition of the ME is provided, and then an analytical solution for the optimal resource allocations α_m^* , $\forall m$ and prices \mathbf{p}^* is derived based on dual decomposition.

A. Market Equilibrium

The ME point is denoted by the tuple (α^*, \mathbf{p}^*) , with $\alpha^* = [\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_m^*, \dots, \alpha_M^*]$, where \mathbf{p}^* is the vector of equilibrium prices and α^* is the vector of equilibrium computing resource allocations to the servers that maximize their utility and at the same time clear the market [12]–[15].

Definition 1. (Market Equilibrium) A resource allocation solution (α^*, \mathbf{p}^*) is an ME if the following conditions hold:

- 1) **Utility Maximization:** Given the equilibrium price vector \mathbf{p}^* , every server receives its optimal resource allocation α_m^* that maximizes its utility U_m subject to its budget constraint, i.e.,

$$\alpha_m^* \in \arg \max_{\substack{\alpha_m \geq 0 \\ \sum_{\forall n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_{n,m} p_n^* \leq B_m}} U_m(\alpha_m), \quad (5)$$

which is known as the "maximum bang-per-buck".

- 2) **Market Clearance:** Either the total computing power F_n of each client n is completely allocated to the servers, i.e., $\sum_{\forall m \in \mathcal{M}} \alpha_{n,m} = 1, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$, or the corresponding client is priced with zero. Furthermore, each server m exhausts its budget B_m .

The first condition captures the rationality of the buyers that compete with each other, targeting to maximize the return on their market investment, as described by their utility function. The second condition declares that either the goods meet the market's demand and are priced, or they are offered for free in the case of being in excess. The equilibrium point is reached only when the buyers exhaust their budget, inducing the maximization of both the servers' and clients' profits.

B. Problem Solution

The ME of the resource allocation problem (4a)-(4c) has been proved to be easily inferred as the optimal solution of the following convex program which is known as the Eisenberg-Gale (EG) program [12]:

$$\max_{\alpha_m, U_m, \forall m} \sum_{\forall m \in \mathcal{M}} B_m \ln(U_m) \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad U_m(\alpha_m) = \sum_{\forall n \in \mathcal{N}} q_{n,m} \alpha_{n,m}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6b)$$

$$\sum_{\forall m \in \mathcal{M}} \alpha_{n,m} \leq 1, \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (6c)$$

$$\alpha_{n,m} \geq 0, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6d)$$

where objective (6a) maximizes the sum of servers' utility logarithms, weighted by their budget B_m . The problem (6a)-(6d) is convex and satisfies Slater's condition, since there always exists a strictly feasible solution $\alpha_{n,m} = \epsilon > 0$, with $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, such that all constraints are met with strict inequality. Consequently, the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions are necessary and sufficient for determining the optimal resource allocation and pricing solution.

It should be noted that while the prices \mathbf{p} do not explicitly appear in the formulation of (6a)-(6d), they can be obtained as the Lagrangian dual variables associated with the clients' total computing power constraints in Eq. (6c). In this way, the prices capture the rate of change of the objective function with any change in the total computing power constraints.

Proposition 1. *The optimal solution to the EG program is the ME for the Fisher market, at which the resource allocation maximizes the servers' utilities while completely exhausting their budgets. Equilibrium prices are guaranteed to exist, and the resulting utilities are unique.*

Proof. Due to space limitations, the detailed proof is omitted but follows standard procedures by analyzing KKT conditions commonly found in the literature [12]–[15]. \square

As already stated, the equilibrium resource allocations α^* can be directly determined by solving the primal problem (6a)-(6d). In the following, we comprehensively present the method to analytically determine the equilibrium prices \mathbf{p}^* by solving the dual problem.

To facilitate the dual problem formulation, the dual variables $p_n, \kappa_m, \lambda_{n,m} \geq 0$ associated with each constraint are introduced. Then, the Lagrangian function of the EG program (6a)-(6d) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}, \alpha, \mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = & \sum_{\forall m} B_m \ln(U_m) + \sum_{\forall n} p_n \left(1 - \sum_{\forall m} \alpha_{n,m} \right) \\ & + \sum_{\forall m} \kappa_m \left(\sum_{\forall n} q_{n,m} \alpha_{n,m} - U_m \right) + \sum_{\forall n} \sum_{\forall m} \lambda_{n,m} \alpha_{n,m}. \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

By defining $f_m(U_m) = -B_m \ln(U_m)$, Eq. (7) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) &= \sum_{\forall m} (-\kappa_m U_m - f_m(U_m)) + \sum_{\forall n} p_n \\ &+ \sum_{\forall n} \sum_{\forall m} (-p_n + \kappa_m q_{n,m} + \lambda_{n,m}) \alpha_{n,m}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Then, the dual problem is formally defined as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda} \geq 0} g(\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) \quad (9)$$

with $g(\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \max_{\mathbf{U}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$ the dual function.

By analyzing the KKT conditions with respect to $\alpha_{n,m}$, we get:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})}{\partial \alpha_{n,m}} = -p_n + \kappa_m q_{n,m} + \lambda_{n,m} = 0, \forall n, m. \quad (10)$$

which also gives $p_n + \kappa_m q_{n,m} = -\lambda_{n,m} \leq 0, \forall n, m$. Thus, $p_n \geq \kappa_m q_{n,m}, \forall n, m$.

By utilizing Eq. (10), the dual function is further simplified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\min_{\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}} \max_{\mathbf{U}} \sum_{\forall m} (-\kappa_m U_m - f_m(U_m)) + \sum_{\forall n} p_n \\ &= \min_{\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}} \sum_{\forall n} p_n + \sum_{\forall m} \max_{\mathbf{U}} (-\kappa_m U_m - f_m(U_m)) \\ &= \min_{\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}} \sum_{\forall n} p_n + \sum_{\forall m} f_m^*(-\kappa_m) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $f_m^*(-\kappa_m)$ is the convex conjugate of $f_m(U_m)$ evaluated at $-\kappa_m$.

Based on the outcomes of Eq. (10)-(11), the dual problem of (6a)-(6d) is given by:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}} \sum_{\forall n} p_n - \sum_{\forall m} B_m \ln(\kappa_m) \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } p_n \geq q_{n,m} \kappa_m, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (12b)$$

$$p_n \geq 0, \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (12c)$$

It can be verified that the KKT conditions for problems (6a)-(6d) and (12a)-(12c) are equivalent, with $\alpha_{n,m}$ serving as the Lagrangian dual variable associated with constraint (12b). Hence, by solving problem (12a)-(12c), the equilibrium prices \mathbf{p}^* can be derived.

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed market-based resource allocation framework, relying on ME point, via modeling and simulation. The evaluation focuses on analyzing the behavior of the derived equilibrium allocations and prices in a multi-server, multi-model FL network, as well as comparing its performance with other widely adopted resource allocation and sharing schemes from the literature. In our simulation experiments, we consider $N = 10$ clients and $M = 4$ servers. We assume that each client possesses a set of $D_n = [400, 500]$ training samples with computational intensity $C_n = [0.08, 0.32]$ GCPU cycles/sample. For fairness purposes and to facilitate subsequent

Fig. 2: Pure evaluation of equilibrium prices for clients with increasing training data and computing resources.

performance evaluation, we consider that, for each model, all clients have approximately the same number of samples with similar computational intensity, i.e., $D_{n,m} = D_n$ and $C_{n,m} = C_n, \forall m$. However, clients differ in their total number of training samples D_n and computational intensity C_n across models. Moreover, the clients are further distinguished in their total computing power availability, considered within the range $F_n = [1, 10]$ GCPU cycles/sec. The local training time threshold is $T_{n,m}^{thr} = [100, 120]$ msec, $\forall n, m$. Last, the servers are characterized by different budgets in the range $B_m = [100, 400]$, which reflect the criticality and priority of their respective models for training. The aforementioned parameter values are used throughout our evaluation unless otherwise explicitly stated.

A. Pure Performance Evaluation

To assess the behavior of the equilibrium resource allocation and prices, we consider a simulation setup with $N = 10$ clients, each characterized by a different number of local training samples and total computing resource capacity, represented by the client ID. A higher ID indicates a greater amount of data and computing resources. First, in Fig. 2, the pricing of the respective client is illustrated as a function of the client ID in the horizontal axis, verifying that clients investing more effort in terms of training samples and computing resources to the overall multi-model FL process are priced more. To further examine how clients allocate their computing resources for training models across different servers, Fig. 3 analyzes three distinct budget ratio scenarios from the perspective of the servers. Consider $M = 4$ servers denoted as S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4 , the budget ratio refers to the relative budget availability of each server compared to server S_1 . For example, a budget ratio of $(1/2/3/4)$ implies that the budget of server S_2 is twice that of server S_1 , the budget of server S_3 is three times the budget of server S_1 , and the budget of server S_4 is four times that of server S_1 . Across the three budget ratio cases examined, Fig. 3 illustrates the equilibrium resource allocations as a function of the client ID along the horizontal axis. The results show that servers with higher IDs and larger budgets can afford to engage more clients, ensuring greater data heterogeneity for improved global model accuracy and faster training times,

Fig. 3: Pure evaluation of equilibrium resource allocations for clients with increasing training data and computing resources under different server budget ratio cases.

Fig. 4: Pure evaluation of achieved (a) server utility and (b) mean model error for increasing budget shift from server S_3 to server S_4 .

reflecting their model’s criticality. By varying the budget ratios of servers, specifically increasing the budget of server S_3 while decreasing that of server S_4 , we demonstrate that the proposed model effectively prioritizes service allocation, where servers with higher budgets receive resources from more clients.

In addition to examining the equilibrium resource allocations and prices, Fig. 4 specifically analyzes the impact of shifting the budget from server S_3 to server S_4 on the utilities and achieved model errors of the different servers, while maintaining the budget ratios of servers S_1 and S_2 constant equal to $(1/2)$. In the horizontal axis of Fig. 4, the budget shift x from one server to another is shown, ranging from 0 to 3 units. Fig. 4a validates that increasing the budget increases the utility and vice versa. In accordance, the error rate (see Eq. (1)) decreases with an increased budget in Fig. 4b, as the respective server can afford to pay more clients, thereby acquiring more diverse and potentially heterogeneous data samples for the FL process, while also investing more in computing resources.

B. Comparative Performance Evaluation

In this section, the proposed resource allocation and pricing solution based on the ME is compared against the following schemes from the literature: (a) Max-Min Fairness: The utility

of the lowest utility server is maximized while ensuring the resource allocation respects the clients’ total computing power constraints; (b) Proportional Sharing: Each server is allocated a fraction of each client’s computing resources proportionally to the server’s budget [17]; (c) Max Social Welfare: The total utility of all servers is maximized subject to the clients’ total computing power constraint, neglecting budget constraints [5], [7]; (d) Equal Sharing: All servers are allocated an equal fraction of each client’s computing resources.

In our experiment, we consider a baseline budget ratio of $(1/2/3/4)$ between the servers, along with $N = 10$ clients, each having increasing values for both data and computing resources, as previously described. Fig. 5 illustrates: (a) the total resource allocations from different clients to the various servers along the x-axis, (b) the achieved server utilities, and (c) the mean local model error across the different server models while accounting for the various comparative scenarios. As expected, the maximum average utility is achieved in the Max Social Welfare scenario (Fig. 5b), albeit at the cost of highly uneven resource allocations from the client side (Fig. 5a) and model errors on the server side (Fig. 5c), failing to fairly respect the service criticality compared to the rest of the scenarios. Equal Sharing, Proportional Sharing, and Max-

Fig. 5: Evaluation of (a) sum equilibrium resource allocations per server, (b) server utilities, and (c) mean model error per server, under the comparative schemes.

Min Fairness do not explicitly account for budget constraints and model criticality. Therefore, although the proposed Market Equilibrium framework performs approximately close to these approaches in terms of server utility and achieved model error, it effectively allocates resources on the client side to align with the servers' model criticality, ensuring that each server's budget is fully utilized.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we introduced a market-based framework for resource allocation in multi-server, multi-model Federated Learning (FL) networks, using it as a case study to explore the interdependencies between clients and providers within the context of 6G networks. By modeling the allocation problem as a Fisher market, we provided a clear and efficient solution for servers to attract clients and maximize model accuracy within server budget constraints and client resource constraints. The analytical solution derived from the convex Eisenberg-Gale program ensures convergence to the Market Equilibrium (ME) point, providing a balanced approach to resource distribution. Our results, validated through comparisons with existing schemes, demonstrate the framework's ability to effectively handle varying budget and resource availabilities, while promoting fair client participation when compared against resource sharing schemes from the literature. Extending the model to address cases where the budget is not exhausted for efficiency, as well as developing distributed solutions, are part of our current and future work.

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